

WATER CONSERVATION BY RAIN WATER HARVESTING

Prof. P.D.Vyas*

Mrs. Sanskriti S. Mujumdar**

ABSTRACT

Water resources scarcity is a major topic of global discussion in recent years. The reasons for water scarcity are misallocation, misuse and degradation of water. Sustainable water management is one of the paramount importance for maintaining economic prosperity and ecological balance.

Rain water is the primary source of water. Ponds, lakes, rivers and ground water are the secondary sources of water. We depend on the secondary sources of water for our requirements. But we forget the point that rain water is the source of recharge or water supply for all these secondary sources of water. We get about 100 hours of rain in a year. It is this 100 hour quantity that must be caught, stored and used over the other 8660 hours that make up a year. If not harvested, the rainwater runs off into the sea or floods low lying areas.

The paper emphasizes on the method of rain water harvesting for water conservation and discusses in detail the various techniques used for rain water harvesting.

Necessity of Water Harvesting

Rainwater is the primary source of water. Ponds, lakes, rivers and ground water are the secondary sources of water. We depend on the secondary sources of water for our requirements. But we forget the point that rain water is the source of recharge or water supply for all these secondary sources of water. We get about 100 hours of rain in a year. It is this 100-hour quantity that must be caught, stored and used over the other 8660 hours that make up a year. If not harvested, the rainwater runs off into the sea or floods low lying areas.

Water harvesting means to understand the value of rain and to make optimum use of rainwater at the place where it falls. In scientific terms, water harvesting refers to collection and storage of rainwater. In general, water harvesting is the activity of direct collection of rainwater. Rainwater harvesting (RWH) is catching rainwater when it falls and storing to use during the non-rainy season. Harvested rainwater can be utilized for several purposes including drinking, washing, gardening, flushing.

Let us take the example of Cherapunji. This place receives 11000 mm of rainfall, which is the maximum in India, and yet there is scarcity of drinking water in this place. This is because rainwater is not conserved but allowed to drain away. Thus we can see that it does not matter how much rain is received but how much water of this rain is stored. So it is not that water harvesting should be done only at places where there is less rainfall.

Alternatively, one may wonder that if the same quantity of water was sufficient for our forefathers and if they never had to do water harvesting, what is the reason that suddenly there is so much crisis and we have to take remedial steps.

* Professor & Head

** Lecturer

The reason behind it is that as compared to that era, the consumption has increased manifold. The reasons for increase in consumption can be listed as follows:

- Population growth.
- Increase in Per capita demand.
- Increase in Agriculture demand.
- Industrial growth.

River water; water in lakes, ponds and wells; water that seeps into the ground, collecting in the belly of the earth; tap water; even bottled water! The source of all water is rain. Understanding this, in order to meet demand, then, what we actually need to do is harvest the rain. The construction of Dams, Canals, and Pipelines etc. are extremely costly and require huge infrastructure setup. But it does not address the problem to that much extent. On the other hand Rainwater Harvesting is the simplest, safest and low cost technology, which a common man can understand and adopt very easily. Moreover it does not require that much technical skill as require in previous case.

Concept of Rain Water Harvesting

The term '**Rainwater Harvesting**' appears to have originated from the word 'harvesting', used to cover all agricultural activities involving cutting, reaping, picking and gathering of grain of value from any fully-grown crop.

Rainwater harvesting may be defined as any human activity involving inducing, collecting, storing and conserving local surface runoff for recharging surface water bodies and ground water or storage of rainwater in some natural or artificial container either for immediate use or use before the onset of the next monsoon. The best example of rainwater harvesting comes from the house at Porbandar in Gujarat where Mahatma Gandhi (the Father of the Nation) was born. The terrace on the top floor of that house, thoroughly washed before the first monsoon showers, served as the rainwater catchment and an underground reservoir with a capacity of around 91 cubic meters served to store water for drinking and other domestic purposes throughout the year, while a pipe having a heap of lime at its mouth served to convey filtered water from the terrace into the reservoir.

Rainwater Harvesting in urban areas, the construction of houses, footpaths and roads has left little exposed earth for water to soak in. In parts of the rural areas of India, floodwater quickly flows to the rivers, which then dry up soon after the rains stop. If this water can be held back, it can seep into the ground and recharge the groundwater supply.

Concept of Rainwater Harvesting

The process of rainwater harvesting involves the following steps:

- Capture the rainwater wherever it falls.
- A major portion of rainwater that falls on the earth's surface runs off from streams to rivers and finally to the sea.
- The technique of rainwater harvesting involves catching the rain from the localized catchment surfaces such as roofs of houses, plain and sloping ground surfaces etc.
- The rainwater that falls on these catchments is diverted into dugout ponds, vessels or underground tanks to store for long periods.
- Construction of small barriers across small streams to check and store the running water is also a method of rain water harvesting.

Error!

Main Purpose of Rain Water Harvesting

- Storage of fresh water
- Conserve Ground Water
- Rejuvenate Aquifer System / Raising declining water table
- Water reclamation
- Flood control
- Water quality preservation and improvement
- Building a barrier against saline and low quality water intrusions
- Subsidence abatement
- Disposal of cooling water
- Disposal of waste water
- Management of water resources

Advantages of Rain Water Harvesting

- The use of aquifers for storage and distribution of water and removal of contaminants by natural cleaning processes which occur as polluted rain and surface water infiltrate the soil and percolate down through the various geological formations
- The technology is appropriate and generally well understood by both the technicians and the general population
- Very few special tools are needed to dig drainage wells
- In rock formations with high, structural integrity few additional materials may be required to construct the wells
- Groundwater recharge stores water during the wet seasons for use in the dry seasons, when demand is highest
- Aquifer water can be improved by recharging with high quality injected water
- Recharge can be significantly increase the sustainable yield of aquifer
- Recharge methods are environmentally attractive, particularly in arid regions.
- Most aquifer recharge systems are easy to operate
- Increase water availability
- Checks the declining water table
- Improves the quality of groundwater through the dilution of fluoride, nitrate and salinity
- Prevents soil erosion and flooding especially in urban areas

Commonly Used Techniques of Rain Water Harvesting

* Use of roofs as catchments

- Roofs made of corrugated iron sheet, asbestos sheet or tiles can be utilized for harvesting the rainwater.
- Gutters and channels can be fixed on the edges of roof all around to collect and transport the rain water from the roof to the storage tank.
- The collected water is filtered through a filter filled with pebbles in the bottom and coarse sand on the top.
- The filtered water is collected either in a storage tank or existing sump. Over flow water may be diverted to an existing open well / bore well.
- If the roof is thatched, polythene sheets can be used for collecting the rainwater.
- The collected rainwater is filtered through a filter filled with pebbles in the bottom and coarse sand on the top.
- The filtered water is collected either in storage tank of existing sump and the overflow water may be diverted to percolation pit nearby.

* Use of Terrace as catchment.

- Guttering system to transport rainwater to storage tanks.
- Covered storage tank above or below ground level. first flow of the rain should be drained to get rid of the dust & contaminants.
- As far as possible storage tanks should be kept underground so that sunlight doesn't reach, to avoid contamination of fresh water.

* Hand pump / Bore well recharge

- Rainwater is collected in stabilization tank to prevent entry of floating debris.
- From stabilization tank, the rainwater flows into bore well.

* By constructing check dam across stream:

- Rainwater can be harvested in a stream by constructing a small size dam to check water (called check dam). Surrounding farms are get their water supply from the water stored in this dam. This type of dam is usually filled 2 to 3 times during monsoon.

Maintenance of Rooftop RWHS

- Just before the arrival of monsoon, the rooftop / catchment area has to be cleaned properly.

- The roof outlet on the terrace should be covered with a mesh to prevent entry of leaves or other solid waste into the system.
- The filter materials have to be either replaced or washed properly before the monsoon.
- The diversion valve has to be opened for the first 5 to 10 minutes of rain to dispose off the polluted first flush.

Conclusions

After discussing the above mentioned facts, we realize the importance of Rain water harvesting and the difference it can make in the way we live. In order to promote water conservation, one can try to implement the following tips:

- Try to do one thing each day that will result in saving water. Don't worry if the savings are minimal because every drop counts! You can make a difference.
- Remember to use only the amount you actually need.
- Encourage your family to keep looking for new ways to conserve water in and around your home.
- Make sure that your home is leak-free. Many homes have leaking pipes that go unnoticed.
- Do not leave the tap running while you are brushing your teeth or soaping your face.
- See that there are no leaks in the toilet tank. You can check this by adding colour to the tank.
- Avoid flushing the toilet unnecessarily.
- You can store water in a variety of ways. A simple method is to place a drum on a raised platform directly under the rainwater collection source. You can also collect water in a bucket during the rainy season.

SAVE WATER –SAVE LIFE